

From Theory to Practice: Mapping Polycentricity in Urban and Regional Studies

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Abstract

Polycentricity has transformed from a normative European planning paradigm into a globally significant research framework shaping urban and regional development debates. To uncover its intellectual structure and evolutionary trajectory, the present research examines the field from two complementary perspectives: (1) the conceptual development of polycentricity and its associated thematic clusters, and (2) the composition of the scientific community alongside the dynamics of its collaboration networks. From more than 800 identified studies, 470 were selected for in-depth bibliometric analysis, revealing four principal intellectual streams: (1) theoretical and structural foundations, (2) functional and environmental implications, (3) network-oriented approaches, and (4) interdisciplinary linkages. The analysis further explores patterns of scholarly collaboration and the spatial distribution of knowledge production. Findings demonstrate that while polycentricity has matured into a global, empirically grounded field, persistent challenges remain, including geographical disparities and increasing sub-field fragmentation. By presenting a holistic analytical framework, this research provides valuable guidance for future scholarship and fosters more integrated approaches to sustainable urban and regional development.

Keywords

Polycentricity;
Bibliometric
Analysis; Territorial
Cohesion;
PageRank;
Intellectual
Structure

Introduction

Polycentricity has emerged as a pivotal concept in urban and regional studies, signifying a shift from monocentric models to more decentralised and networked urban forms (Lan et al., 2019). As cities worldwide grapple with rapid growth, sprawl, and functional diversification, polycentric development is increasingly advocated as a strategy to enhance productivity (Meijers et al., 2018; Li & Liu, 2018), bolster economic resilience (Lorens & Gołędzinowska, 2022; Gurría-Gascón et al., 2024; Ao et al., 2025), reduce congestion (Li et al., 2018; Lotfi et al., 2022), and promote sustainability, cohesion, or reduce regional inequality (Chen et al., 2019; Meijers & Sandberg, 2008; Shahabi Shahmiri & Khodabandeh, 2025). This spatial pattern cuts across disciplines like urban planning, geography, economics, and transport research; however, its

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definition remains contested. Recent studies highlight its "fuzzy" conceptual boundaries and varied operationalisation across different contexts (Bartosiewicz & Marcińczak, 2020; Möck & Küpper, 2020; Rauhut, 2017; Veneri & Burgalassi, 2012).

This link to 'cohesion' is fundamental, as polycentricity is deeply intertwined with the European policy goal of Territorial Cohesion (Meijers & Sandberg, 2021). Emerging from a similar European planning background, Territorial Cohesion was introduced alongside economic and social cohesion to promote harmonious and balanced development (Medeiros & Rauhut, 2018; Zaucha & Böhme, 2019). Key European policy frameworks, such as the Territorial Agenda, explicitly identify 'polycentric development' as a core strategy for achieving Territorial Cohesion. In this view, fostering a 'more polycentric urban system' is considered a key component of the Territorial Cohesion process (Möck & Küpper, 2019; Rauhut, 2017). However, much like polycentricity itself, Territorial Cohesion has also been criticized for being an ambiguous and 'fuzzy' concept, making its operationalisation and measurement a significant challenge for academics and policymakers (Demeterova et al., 2020; Möck & Küpper, 2019).

The ambiguity surrounding polycentricity stems from divergent definitions, measurement challenges, and a disconnect between policy and reality. Research has demonstrated that scale-dependency is a primary reason for the varied and often conflicting definitions of polycentricity (Liu et al., 2018; Schmitt et al., 2015). For instance, a city may be polycentric at one scale (e.g., intra-urban) but entirely monocentric at another (e.g., national) (Liu et al., 2018). Furthermore, different disciplines approach polycentricity from distinct perspectives and with different focal points. Economists, for example, emphasise agglomeration effects (Li et al., 2022), planners focus on land use (Pan et al., 2024), and geographers analyse flows, leading to contradictory metrics (Vasanen, 2013).

While the use of multiple and diverse criteria (Bartosiewicz & Marcińczak, 2020) can be considered a conventional measurement challenge, data limitations and the dynamic nature of urban polycentricity compound this issue. Although traditional metrics like population distribution are often available, they neglect functional linkages. In contrast, recent advancements in data analytics—particularly the use of big data from smart travel cards and probabilistic modelling—have enabled more precise measurements of polycentricity (Wang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). However, due to difficulties in accessing such data across different world regions, they are not always suitable for comparative studies. Moreover, polycentricity evolves over time (e.g., Seoul's rapid decentralization versus London's slower transformation), which complicates static analyses and highlights the role of data-driven methods in redefining urban structures (He et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021).

A further challenge related to polycentricity is the misalignment between policies and existing realities. While policies such as the European Spatial Development Perspective (ESDP) often promote polycentricity (Commission et al., 1999), market forces may reinforce monocentric patterns, such as the clustering of high-value services in primary cores (Davoudi, 2003; Živanović et al., 2021). Additionally, the evidence regarding the effectiveness and efficiency of polycentric policies remains ambiguous and contradictory (Dadashpoor et al., 2023). For example, recent research suggests that while polycentricity can reduce congestion, it may also increase carbon emissions from longer inter-regional commutes (Burgalassi & Luzzati, 2015; Liu et al., 2025).

To position this work, we move beyond a conventional descriptive bibliometric analysis. This study is situated within an epistemological framework, aiming not only to quantify outputs but to critically map the 'intellectual structure' and 'paradigmatic shifts' within polycentricity research. Whereas prior bibliometric studies in urban research (Sharma & Kumar, 2025; Tiwari & Vajpeyi, 2023) have often focused on descriptive trends, we seek to clarify how the field's conceptual contributions have evolved, identifying dominant schools of thought and hidden knowledge gaps. Accordingly, this study is guided by two central research questions: (1) What is the underlying intellectual structure of polycentricity research, including its dominant thematic clusters, most influential actors, and key conceptual pillars? And (2) How has this structure evolved over time, and what does this evolution—particularly the geographical and methodological shifts—reveal about the field's paradigmatic gaps and future trajectories? Our guiding hypothesis is that polycentricity has transformed from a normative, European-centric planning concept into a fragmented, empirically-driven global field. We posit that this transformation has been accompanied by a geographical bias in knowledge production and the 'siloeing' of sub-fields, creating a divergence between foundational (highly-cited) knowledge and recent (high-impact, network-based) applied research. By addressing these questions, this analysis ultimately provides a critical roadmap to guide future research and policy.

Methods

Research Method and Data Collection

Bibliometric analysis, which can be seen as a complement to systematic literature reviews, focuses on organising the literature of a subject and examining the influence of scientific communities, theoretical approaches, and research frontiers, unlike reviews that concentrate on the theoretical and conceptual aspects of a field (Morales et al., 2025). The bibliometric method provides a quantitative analysis of written publications (Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015). This

method (Figure 1), often utilising computational processing, is used for extracting and examining data based on content or citation analysis, which has led to a significant increase in publications in this area in recent years (Wallin, 2005).

Figure 1 - Bibliometric method (source: Authors' elaboration)

With its quantitative nature, the bibliometric technique aids in the study of scientific and research communities by offering a broader assessment of contributions and authors (Silva & Teixeira, 2008). Several indicators are commonly used in data analysis, such as the total number of publications, most cited documents, co-occurrence networks, thematic evolution, and most prolific authors. This research evaluates the concept of polycentric spatial structure using the Scopus database for the period 2000-2025 (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Research Design Flowchart (source: Authors' elaboration)

Data Processing

The aim of this research is to examine the concept of polycentric spatial structure. Initially, we used the query "TITLE-ABS-KEY (polycentricity) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND LANGUAGE (english)" to identify studies that mentioned the term "polycentricity" in their title, abstract, or keywords. This first step yielded 890 studies. After filtering for English-language journal articles, this number was reduced to 708. Due to the polysemy of the word "polycentricity", studies addressing the concept of polycentricity in governance (Ostrom, 2010) were also included in the initial search, which reduced data quality and increased the number of irrelevant studies. To minimise processing errors, the authors used the Bibliometrix library (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017) in RStudio to remove studies where the author was "Ostrom" or where the terms "Polycentric System" or "Polycentric Governance" appeared in the abstract, title, or keywords. Following this filter and a manual review in Microsoft Excel, the total number of studies included in the analysis was reduced to 470.

Table 1 - Summary of polycentricity literature (2000-2025)

MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2000 : 2025
Sources (Journals, Books, etc.)	212
Documents	470
Annual Growth Rate %	6.36
Document Average Age	6.8
Average citations per doc	30.46
Average citations per year per doc	3.447
DOCUMENT TYPES	
article	470
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	1243
Author's Keywords (DE)	1296
AUTHORS	
Authors	870
Author Appearances	1282
Authors of single-authored docs	105
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	116
Documents per Author	0.54
Co-Authors per Doc	2.73

Table 1 - Continued

MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
International co-authorships %	23.62

Initial Data Statistics

Table 1 provides an overview of the 470 studies included in this research. The present bibliometric analysis explores the scientific literature related to the concept of polycentricity from 2000 to 2025. In this study, 470 scientific articles from 212 reputable sources were analysed. The findings indicate that this field of study is on an upward trend, with an annual growth rate of 6.36%, and the average age of the published articles is 6.8 years. Each article has received an average of 30.46 citations, demonstrating the significant impact of these studies, with an average of 3.447 citations per article per year. Among these studies, 1,243 system-generated keywords (Keywords Plus) and 1,296 author-defined keywords were identified, showcasing the conceptual richness of the field. The active scientific community in this area consists of 870 researchers, who have a total of 1,282 authorship contributions. Of these, 105 researchers have published single-authored papers, and 116 articles were written by a single author. The scientific collaboration pattern shows that each researcher contributed to an average of 0.54 articles, and each article was the result of collaboration among an average of 2.73 authors. Furthermore, 23.62% of the articles were produced through international collaborations, indicating the global nature of this research field.

Figure 3 - Annual scientific production trend in the field of polycentricity (2000–2025) (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Results

Annual Scientific Production Trend

An analysis of the temporal distribution of articles on polycentricity over a 26-year period (2000–2025) reveals significant growth in research interest in this concept (Figure 3). As the data show, the number of articles began at three in the year 2000 and has fluctuated, but the overall trend is clearly upward. The growth accelerated markedly from the late 2010s (around 2018), peaking in 2022 with 55 articles and in 2024 with 61 articles. This surge in scholarly attention likely reflects the transformation of polycentricity from a conceptual idea into a practical application for managing metropolitan challenges and achieving more sustainable regional development. This has been facilitated by concurrent advancements in spatial analysis tools and access to more precise spatial data. The average annual growth rate of 6.36% further confirms this sustained increase in academic focus on the field of polycentricity. (Note: The statistics for 2025 are incomplete as the year is not yet over).

Author Influence: Scientific Structure, Networks, and Hierarchies

A bibliometric analysis of the polycentricity field reveals a distinct structure in its knowledge production. This structure can be analysed across several layers.

Concentration of Production and the Quantity-versus-Quality Trade-off

Scientific production in this field is highly concentrated; only 15 authors (out of a total of 870) have published more than five articles, indicating a degree of relative monopoly and high specialisation. This concentration creates a significant gap between prolific researchers and the majority of authors who have limited contributions (mean of 1.47 and median of 1 article per author).

Amid this, the difference between the most prolific and the most influential authors reveals an interesting pattern. While Derudder B. and Sun B. have the highest output with 18 articles each, the most influential researcher is Meijers E., who, with only 9 articles, has an average of 140 citations per paper. Similarly, Burger M.J. demonstrates extremely high impact, with 4 articles and an average of 167.75 citations. This finding indicates that the quantity and quality of scientific output do not necessarily correlate; some researchers have had a more profound impact on the field with fewer but more foundational papers. Fractional ranking analysis confirms this complexity; for example, Veneri P., who is not in the top 10 for total publications, ranks seventh in fractional authorship due to extensive collaborations (Table 2).

Table 2 - Most Productive Authors

Rank	Authors	Articles	Authors	Articles Fractionalized
1	DERUDDER	18	LI Y	5.78
2	SUN	18	DERUDDER	5.09
3	LI Y	14	SUN	4.98
4	ZHANG	14	MEIJERS	4.62
5	LI W	13	WANG M	4.46
6	LIU X	13	LI W	4.03
7	WANG M	13	VENERI P	4.00
8	WANG Y	9	ZHANG T	3.95
9	MEIJERS	8	LIU X	3.82
10	LIU Y	7	BLOMMAERT J	3.33

Scientific Leaders Based on the h-index

An analysis of the h-index, which measures both quantity and quality, reveals valuable insights (Figure 4). The median h-index is 4 and the mean is 4.76, indicating that half of the active researchers have limited impact. Derudder B. (h-index of 13) and Sun B. (h-index of 12) are considered the scientific leaders in this field. The distribution of the h-index, ranging from 1 to 13, confirms the diversity in impact levels and the formation of a clear scientific hierarchy within the field.

Figure 4 - Distribution of h-index among authors in polycentricity research (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Collaboration Network Analysis: Distinct Clusters and Communication Bridges

The scientific collaboration network, comprising 793 authors and 1,471 connections, has a low density (0.004). This characteristic, along with the relatively high network diameter (13), suggests the existence of distinct yet interconnected research clusters. In this structure, authors like Derudder B. (with a degree centrality of 31 and betweenness centrality of 11,500), Wang M., and Li Y. play a vital role as "communication bridges" between these different clusters.

The collaboration patterns also point to the formation of research groups with specific approaches. The strongest collaborative link is between Sun B. and Zhang T., with 11 co-authored papers, potentially indicating a distinct school of thought. Similarly, Derudder B.'s multiple collaborations with Caset F. and Witlox F. suggest the presence of strong and stable research centres.

Sociological Interpretation: The Formation of a Scientific Field

From the perspective of the sociology of science and in line with Bourdieu's theory of the scientific field (Bourdieu, 1975), the field of polycentricity studies is still in formation. The concentration of scientific production in the hands of a few researchers indicates an accumulation of scientific capital and the establishment of a hierarchy, which could pose a barrier to new researchers. However, the presence of pivotal researchers who act as intermediaries and the low network density suggest that there are ample opportunities for expanding scientific collaboration and distributing scientific capital. These findings underscore that promoting the principles of polycentricity could help lower entry barriers and increase dynamism within this scientific field.

Author Affiliations: The Geography of Power in Knowledge Production

Analysis of author affiliations reveals the geographical distribution of polycentricity knowledge production at national (Figure 5) and institutional levels.

Figure 5 - Geographic distribution of polycentricity studies by country (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

National Level: China's Dominance and Conceptual Bias Risk

China dominates with 437 researcher and 24.47% of publications, reflecting massive investments in megacities and polycentric regions (Liu & Wang, 2016). The gap between China and the USA with 177 researcher and 15.96% of publications indicates a shift in knowledge production towards East Asia. The top five countries (China, USA, UK, Netherlands, Germany) produce 40.37% of articles, while the top ten account for 70.2%, creating a knowledge monopoly that risks treating leading countries' experiences as global norms. Europe's prominence reflects its polycentric planning history (Hall & Pain, 2006). Hong Kong's contribution (2.34%) stems from its polycentric nature (Li et al., 2023), while Iran ranks 17th (1.49%). The minimal African and Latin American representation creates gaps in understanding developing regions' patterns, risking scientific colonialism (Hess, 1995).

Institutional Level: University Concentration

East China Normal University (70 contributions) and Ghent University (52) lead institutionally. Five Chinese universities in the top ten confirm national dominance, reflecting macro-policies on urban research (Liu & Wang, 2016). Dutch universities (Delft, Twente, Erasmus) contribute 63 papers combined, rooted in Netherlands' spatial planning experience and evident in Germany's Rhine-Ruhr region (Eskelinen & Fritsch, 2009). American institutions show dispersed patterns despite second-place ranking. Iran's Tarbiat Modares University (14 contributions) represents a regional hub. The top twenty institutions dominate output, enhancing synergy but risking discursive monopoly. These findings emphasise strengthening international collaborations, particularly with developing countries, to contextualise polycentric concepts globally.

Mainstreaming of Knowledge: Analysis of Leading Publishers and Journals

The bibliometric analysis shows that knowledge related to polycentricity is heavily dominated by a few major international publishers. Elsevier (with 104 articles), Springer (79 articles), and Routledge (60 articles) are the main players in this field. This high concentration in a few major publishers indicates the mainstreaming of polycentricity discussions in the global academic literature.

At the journal level (Figure 6), three journals—*Cities* (with 27 articles), *Urban Studies* (25 articles), and *Regional Studies* (24 articles)—are identified as the most important outlets for these studies. Beyond this core, the publication pattern in other journals reveals different dimensions of the field:

- **European Roots:** The strong presence of the journal *European Planning Studies* (with 19 articles) highlights the particular importance and historical roots of this concept in European

spatial planning, where polycentricity was introduced as a strategy to balance competitiveness and territorial cohesion.

- **Link to Sustainability:** The significant position of the journal Sustainability (with 18 articles) indicates the growing link between the concept of polycentricity and approaches to sustainable urban and regional development, which has gained more importance in recent years.
- **Methodological Evolution:** The presence of specialised journals in spatial technologies, such as Computers, Environment and Urban Systems, confirms the growing trend of using advanced quantitative methods, big data, and GIS in polycentricity studies.

Figure 6 - Leading journals in publishing polycentricity research (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Overall, this publication pattern suggests that polycentricity studies are in a mature phase, having evolved from a purely theoretical concept in generalist journals to a practical framework in more specialised journals, linked to contemporary urban challenges like climate change, urban resilience, and social inclusion.

Intellectual Pillars of the Field: A Review of Highly Cited Studies

An examination of the 10 most-cited articles clearly illuminates the intellectual evolution and conceptual milestones of the field. This journey begins with the foundational article by Simin Davoudi (2003), which critically traced the transition of polycentricity from an "analytical tool" to a "normative and policy agenda" in European spatial planning, profoundly influencing subsequent research.

Following this theoretical groundwork, the literature developed two main analytical approaches: the morphological approach (focusing on the physical distribution of centres) and the functional approach (examining relationships and connections between centres). The paper by Burger & Meijers (2012) made a key contribution by providing a framework to link these two approaches, showing that most regions are more polycentric morphologically than functionally.

These analytical approaches were accompanied by methodological advancements. Green (2007) introduced more formal definitions and metrics for polycentricity using social network analysis, while more recent studies, like the work of Liu et al. (2016), applied sophisticated spatial data analysis techniques to examine the concept in the context of China's rapid urbanization, extending its application from Europe to a global scale.

Concurrently, empirical research increasingly focused on testing the promised benefits of polycentricity. For example, Meijers & Burger (2010) found that polycentricity is associated with higher labour productivity, although they noted that networks of small cities cannot fully replace the agglomeration benefits of a single metropolis. The most recent trend, represented by Burger et al. (2014), emphasises the concept of "multiplexity" in urban networks, showing that different types of functional links (such as commuting or business relationships) create different spatial patterns, complicating our understanding of polycentricity.

Ultimately, this highly cited literature portrays a field that has evolved from initial conceptual debates towards complex empirical analyses and a growing focus on the challenges of measuring and verifying the benefits of polycentric development.

Keyword Analysis: Decoding the Conceptual DNA and Emerging Trends

An analysis of keywords associated with polycentricity reveals the field's conceptual map and its internal dynamics (Table 3). This analysis can be examined in three layers: the conceptual core, the thematic landscape, and the dynamics of the research field.

Table 3 - The most popular keywords

Word	Frequency
Polycentricity	241
Urban spatial structure	47
China	38
Spatial structure	25
Urban form	19
Monocentricity	17
Functional polycentricity	13
Commuting	12
Urban structure	12
GERMANY	10

Conceptual Core: Key Concepts and Theoretical Dichotomies

At the centre of this field, a few key concepts and theoretical oppositions shape the main discourse:

- **Focal Concept:** The keyword "polycentricity" (241 occurrences) stands as the central concept, having experienced gradual but continuous growth. A turning point for this growth was 2015, likely related to the increased global attention on sustainable urban development (Hassan & Lee, 2015; Klopp & Petretta, 2017).
- **Main Theoretical Dichotomy:** The duality of "polycentricity" and "monocentricity" (17 occurrences) marks a fundamental debate in the field. The focus on monocentricity in recent years (2018–2019 and 2022–2023) could be linked to a critical rethinking of the utility of polycentric models in certain contexts (Değerli Çifçi & Duran, 2025; Huo et al., 2024).
- **Internal Conceptual Distinction:** The distinction between "functional polycentricity" (13 occurrences) (Green, 2007; Vasanen, 2012) and "morphological polycentricity" (7 occurrences) (Bartosiewicz & Marcińczak, 2020; Taubenböck et al., 2017) highlights the complexity and multidimensionality of the concept. The increased attention to functional polycentricity since 2018 indicates a shift towards understanding flows and interactions rather than focusing solely on physical aspects.

Thematic Landscape: From Structure to Practical Applications

An examination of high-frequency keywords shows that the dominant discourse is formed around "urban," "spatial," and "structure." The presence of terms like "evidence" and "analysis" confirms the empirical and analytical nature of these studies, while "development" and "planning" emphasise their practical applications.

Within this landscape, several thematic links are prominent:

- **Geographical Focus:** The keyword "China" (38 occurrences) shows that the country's urban transformations have become a key laboratory for testing polycentricity theories (Liu et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2025).
- **Link with Urban Mobility:** The significant connection between the keywords "employment," "commuting," and "transport" highlights the importance of mobility patterns and urban flows in these studies (Jun, 2020; Modarres, 2011; Veneri, 2010).
- **Link with Sustainability:** The presence of the keyword "emissions" signifies the growing connection of these studies with environmental concerns (Khodabandeh & Shahabi Shahmiri, 2025).

Field Dynamics: Coherence, Innovation, and Emerging Trends

The high diversity of keywords (1,350 unique items) and the existence of 1,146 keywords with only a single occurrence (about 85%) reveal a dual characteristic of the field (Figure 7). On one hand, this diversity indicates creativity and innovation among researchers in combining this concept with other areas. On the other hand, it could also suggest a lack of conceptual

coherence and a fragmentation of research efforts. An average of 4.55 keywords per article also confirms that researchers generally seek to combine concepts, which, while enriching the theory, carries the risk of "conceptual dilution."

Recent trends show that the field has a high capacity for adapting to new challenges. The connection of polycentricity with topics like COVID-19 (Abozeid & AboElatta, 2021; Schmahmann et al., 2022), air pollution (Khodabandeh & Shahabi Shahmiri, 2025), innovation (Li & Du, 2022), and advanced producer services is increasing. This demonstrates the dynamism of the concept and its capacity to engage with new development discourses.

Figure 7 - Keyword cloud (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

PageRank Analysis: Hidden Trends and the Evolution of Influence in the Knowledge Network

While traditional methods of article evaluation, such as citation counting, have limitations (Walton, 1999), network-based methods like the PageRank algorithm offer a more nuanced picture of influence. This algorithm, first introduced for ranking web pages in Google (Brin & Page, 1998), is also applied in bibliometric analyses. Its core logic is that the value of an article is measured not just by the number of citations it receives, but by the credibility and quality of the articles that cite it. In other words, a citation from a high-ranking article carries more weight (Chen et al., 2007). More advanced versions of this algorithm have even been used to evaluate authors, yielding more precise results than the h-index (Senanayake et al., 2015; Walker et al., 2007).

The citation network was constructed from the extracted bibliographic data. Using the R programming language and the *igraph* and *dplyr* packages, the PageRank score for each article was calculated. The formula for the calculation is defined as follows:

$$\frac{PR(T_i)}{C(T_i)} \sum_{i=1}^n d + \frac{d-1}{N} = PR(A)$$

In this formula, $PR(A)$ represents the PageRank of article A ; d is the damping factor, which determines the probability of following a citation path; N is the total number of articles (nodes) in the network; and T_i are the articles that cite A . $C(T_i)$ represents the total number of articles that article T_i references. The first component of the formula models the probability of a user randomly selecting any article, while the second component is the sum of the PageRank share transferred from the citing articles to the target article.

Based on empirical findings showing that citation paths in scientific networks are typically short, a damping factor (d) of 0.5 was used to provide a more realistic reflection of how knowledge disseminates (Chen et al., 2007).

Key Finding: Divergence Between Highly Cited and High-PageRank Articles

The analysis of the results table 4 reveals a surprising and significant finding: there is no meaningful overlap between the list of top articles by citation count and the list of top articles by PageRank score. This lack of overlap indicates two different pathways of influence and evolution in this research field.

Table 4 - Top 10 papers by PageRank score and citation count

PageRank Score		Citation Count	
Article	Page Rank	Article	Total Citation
(Yang et al., 2024)	0.002126758	(Davoudi, 2003)	483
(Yang et al., 2012)	0.002126284	(Burger & Meijers, 2012)	366
(Bell & Fisher, 2020)	0.002125855	(Meijers & Burger, 2010)	348
(Zhou et al., 2022)	0.002125558	(Green, 2007)	286
(Blommaert, 2007)	0.002124906	(Liu & Wang, 2016)	233
(Liu et al., 2017)	0.002124866	(Liu et al., 2016)	228
(Li et al., 2022)	0.002124717	(Lee, 2007)	212
(Schmitt, 2013)	0.002124321	(Vasanen, 2012)	196
(Legras, 2015)	0.002124048	(Meijers, 2008)	193
(Zhang & Derudder, 2019)	0.002123880	(Burger et al., 2014)	180

Highly Cited Articles: The Theoretical and Classic Pillars of the Field

The most-cited articles are predominantly works published between 2003 and 2016 that formed the theoretical foundations of the polycentricity field. Davoudi's (2003) article, with 483 citations, leads the list by explaining the initial concepts in European spatial planning. Other

prominent articles, such as the work of Burger & Meijers (2012) on the relationship between form and function, and Meijers & Burger (2010) on spatial structure and productivity, have established the primary frameworks for studies in this area. These are classic works with widespread recognition across the entire scientific community.

High-PageRank Articles: Communication Bridges in Applied and Recent Research

In contrast, articles with high PageRank scores (approaching 0.0021) are mostly newer (published between 2007 and 2024) and have a more applied approach. Articles such as the work of Yang et al. (2024) on productivity in Chinese urban areas, Zhou et al. (2022) on the impact of transport on housing prices in Beijing, and Li et al. (2022) with a meta-analysis of economic performance, are examples that apply theoretical concepts to specific, regional contexts. These articles do not necessarily have high overall citation counts but have been more influential within specialised networks and recent research, acting as communication bridges. The articles by Zhang & Derudder (2019) and Liu et al. (2017) are also examples from this group.

Interpreting the Divergence: A Transition from Theory to Practice and from West to East

This pattern indicates a transition in the polycentricity field from theorisation to practical application. It also clearly shows a geographical shift in studies from a focus on Europe and America (in highly cited articles) towards other regions like China (in high-PageRank articles). These findings highlight the importance of using diverse metrics in evaluating scientific impact, as each method reveals a different facet of importance and influence. Analysing both metrics provides a deeper understanding of the knowledge structure and evolutionary trends in the field of polycentricity studies.

Figure 8 - Article citation network based on PageRank analysis (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Figure 8 presents the PageRank citation network, where each node represents an article, each edge shows a citation relationship between two works, and node size indicates influence scores based on citation patterns.

The spatial distribution of nodes and links in the PageRank network also confirms that knowledge in this field is distributed across a broad, less hierarchical network rather than being concentrated around a few core articles, which itself may reflect the interdisciplinary and multifaceted nature of polycentricity studies.

Conceptual Structure and Thematic Evolution

This section analyses the polycentricity discourse from two perspectives: a static snapshot of its current conceptual map and a dynamic analysis of its evolution.

Figure 9 - Conceptual map of polycentricity based on thematic axes (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

The Conceptual Map of Polycentricity

The field's current knowledge structure is anchored by the focal concepts of "polycentricity" and "China." The high betweenness centrality of "polycentricity" and "urban area" confirms their pivotal roles as bridges connecting diverse sub-fields. Thematic mapping delineates four primary

research axes (Figure 9): a Foundational Axis ("urban spatial structure," "monocentricity"), an Applied Axis focusing on the relationship between "urban form" and "commuting" (Alqhatani et al., 2014; Schwanen et al., 2001), an Emerging Axis ("urban networks," "polycentricity"), and an Interdisciplinary Axis linking to economics and globalisation studies ("innovation," "economic development") (Rauhut, 2017; Sun et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2017). This structure is corroborated by a walktrap algorithm cluster analysis (Figure 10), which identifies two main communities and reflects the field's complexity (Derudder et al., 2022; Kloosterman & Musterd, 2001).

Figure 10 - Concept clustering of polycentricity using the Walktrap algorithm (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Further analysis shows that polycentricity is articulated across four dimensions: morphological (Jung et al., 2022; Li et al., 2018), functional (Vasanen, 2012), policy (Liu et al., 2018), and scale (Kloosterman & Musterd, 2001; Schmitt, 2013). Its interdisciplinary applications are strong, with linkages to transport (Bentlage et al., 2021), economics (Garcia-López & Muñoz, 2010; Zhang et al., 2017), environmental studies (Khodabandeh & Shahabi Shahmiri, 2025), and quality of life (Bertram & Chilla, 2023).

Thematic Evolution of the Discourse

The discourse on polycentricity has evolved significantly between 2000 and 2025. The Inception Period (2000–2004) (Figure 11) was characterized by a focus on European regional

studies, where the concept was still formative (Davoudi, 2003; Kloosterman & Musterd, 2001; Parr, 2004). During the Transition Period (2005–2009) (Figure 12), attention shifted towards economic concepts, with "ADVANCED PRODUCER SERVICES" emerging as a key factor (Hoyler, Kloosterman, & Sokol, 2008).

Figure 11 - Thematic evolution maps of polycentricity in 5-year intervals (2000–2004) (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Figure 12 - Thematic evolution maps of polycentricity in 5-year intervals (2005–2009) (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Figure 13 - Thematic evolution maps of polycentricity in 5-year intervals (2010–2014) (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Figure 14 - Thematic evolution maps of polycentricity in 5-year intervals (2015–2019) (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000-2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

The Transformation Period (2010–2014) (Figure 13) marked a conceptual leap towards understanding spatial-functional dynamics, with concepts like "COMMUTING" becoming central and China emerging as a key case study (Garcia-López & Muñiz, 2010; Modarres, 2011; Veneri, 2010). In the Maturity Period (2015–2019) (Figure 14), "POLYCENTRICITY" itself became a core keyword, and the focus on planning applications and research on China reached its peak (Li et al., 2018; Liu & Wang, 2016; Zhang & Derudder, 2019).

Figure 15 - Thematic evolution maps of polycentricity in 5-year intervals (2020–2025) - (source: Authors' analysis based on Scopus data, 2000–2025, using R, bibliometrix package)

Finally, the Recent Period (2020–2025) (Figure 15) is defined by complexity and specialisation, with the rise of advanced methods like "SPATIOTEMPORAL ANALYSIS" (Bartosiewicz & Marcińczak, 2020; Caset et al., 2023; Li et al., 2024). This evolutionary path, which shows a geographical diversification from Europe to China (Ao et al., 2025; Bartosiewicz & Marcińczak, 2020), reflects the increasing complexity of contemporary urban spaces.

The analysis of these trends, including topics with burst growth (Table 5), highlights polycentricity as a vital analytical framework.

Table 5 - Topics with burst growth

Keyword	Max Growth Rate	Burst Period	Total Frequency
Advanced Producer Services	40	2005-2009	6

Table 5 - continued

Keyword	Max Growth Rate	Burst Period	Total Frequency
Commuting	50		12
Urban Spatial Structure	50		47
China	40	2010-2014	38
Germany	40		10
Metropolitan Areas	40		7
Urban Structure	40		12
Accessibility	40		9
Chinese Cities	40		6
Decentralization	40	2015-2019	6
Dispersion	40		5
Economic Performance	40		6
Economic Development	40		4
Machine Learning	40	2020-2025	4
Connectivity	30		5

Discussion: Mapping the Evolution of Polycentric Urban Studies—Insights from a Bibliometric Analysis

From Margin to Mainstream: The Mainstreaming and Paradigmatic Evolution of Polycentricity

This study confirms that polycentricity has evolved from a theoretical concept in European spatial planning (Davoudi, 2003) into a globally applied analytical framework. This mainstreaming is evidenced by substantial post-2010 growth in publications (6.36% annually) and citations (averaging 30.46 per article), driven by escalating urbanization challenges and advancements in information technology (e.g., GIS, big data) that facilitate empirical testing of polycentricity's core hypotheses regarding efficiency, sustainability, and equity.

Methodologically, the field has progressed from early morphological descriptions (e.g., Burger & Meijers, 2012) to sophisticated analyses of functional linkages (e.g., commuting networks) and sustainability outcomes. This shift has prompted critical reevaluation of the traditional polycentric-monocentric dichotomy, with recent research emphasising context-dependent factors such as urban scale, socio-economic conditions, and governance capacity.

Cutting-edge tools—including machine learning, spatio-temporal modelling, and advanced network analyses (e.g., PageRank)—are now uncovering nuanced knowledge flows and enabling precise assessment of economic and environmental impacts. Seminal collaborations, such as those by Sun and Zhang on economic performance and PM2.5, and the Ghent school on agglomeration externalities, exemplify this frontier research, guiding future empirical and policy directions.

The Geopolitics of Knowledge: Geographical Imbalance and the Risk of Discursive Monopoly

Bibliometric results reveal persistent geographical disparities in knowledge production. Initially rooted in Western contexts like the Randstad, Rhine-Ruhr, and Bay Area (Harrison et al., 2020), the field was long dominated by European and North American institutions, as reflected in publishing patterns and citation concentrations pre-2017.

As polycentricity globalised, non-Western regions—particularly China—often entered literature merely as case studies, subjected to uncritical application of Western frameworks. This approach risks overlooking distinct spatial-economic characteristics, such as scale differences between Chinese and European contexts.

Such imbalances reinforce a "discursive monopoly" (Bourdieu, 1975), where epistemic authority remains concentrated among elite researchers (e.g., Derudder, Meijers, Sun) and institutional hubs (e.g., East China Normal University, Ghent University). The central concern is thus not only analytical validity but also the power dynamics that determine whose experiences legitimise urban theory. Emerging critiques from the Global South, however, may signal a shift toward greater balance.

The Evolution of Scientific Influence: From General Reputation to Networked Impact

The divergence between PageRank and citation metrics reflects an evolution in scientific influence: from broad, foundational contributions to specialised, networked knowledge. Highly cited articles establish the field's theoretical core but often lack direct links to contemporary research.

In contrast, high PageRank studies—typically newer and produced by leading groups—function as bridges across knowledge clusters. For instance, Yang et al. (2024) connect agglomeration effects with productivity through advanced simulations, integrating economic geography and regional policy. Increasing post-2017 collaborations between European and Chinese researchers further illustrate this trend toward integrative, networked scholarship.

The Internal Structure of the Discourse: Thematic Islands and Paradigmatic Gaps

Co-occurrence network analysis reveals a strongly clustered intellectual structure, indicating significant siloing within the field. While specialisation fosters depth, it also inhibits interdisciplinary exchange and intellectual integration.

Key conceptual clusters highlight central tensions:

- The Form-Commuting-Polycentricity cluster interrogates morphology's influence on mobility;
- The Sprawl-Polycentricity cluster exposes tensions between spontaneous decentralization and planned polycentricity;
- Other clusters reflect shifts from description to intervention, organic vs. planned development (e.g., Germany vs. China), and relational paradigms emphasising urban networks.

These clusters further reveal three paradigmatic gaps:

1. Scale Gap: between metropolitan and system-level analyses;
2. Methodological Gap: from static to dynamic, simulation-based approaches;
3. West-East Gap: between incremental participatory models and large-scale engineered planning.

Policy Implications and Relevance

Critical research gaps include insufficient attention to social dimensions (e.g., justice, cohesion) and weak innovation-polycentricity linkages. Future progress necessitates deeper integration with network science, urban sociology, and economic geography. This intellectual structure embodies the field's historical trajectory: from European regional studies to Sino-focused functional analyses, culminating in today's methodological pluralism and thematic diversity.

The findings of this bibliometric analysis carry significant policy relevance by highlighting critical gaps and biases in the knowledge base that informs urban and regional planning. The pronounced geographical concentration of research, heavily skewed towards Chinese and European contexts, serves as a crucial warning against the uncritical transfer of polycentric models to other regions, particularly in the Global South, where a context-specific evidence base is largely absent. Furthermore, the intellectual 'siloing' identified between thematic clusters—such as the disconnect between morphological-physical planning and socio-functional dynamics—alerts policymakers to the dangers of fragmented interventions. A policy focus solely on physical form (e.g., developing new centres) without an integrated approach that considers functional connectivity (e.g., transport) and, critically, social outcomes (e.g., spatial justice, cohesion) is likely to be ineffective. This research thus underscores the urgent need for a more

holistic and integrated policy framework. Finally, the identified 'discursive monopoly' issues a call to action for funding agencies to actively promote inclusive international collaborations, which are essential for building the diverse, robust, and globally-relevant evidence base required to guide sustainable 21st-century urban development.

Conclusion: Polycentricity as a Conceptual Palimpsest- Pathways for a Mature yet Fragmented Field

This study has conceptualised the evolution of polycentricity research as a scholarly palimpsest, wherein new layers of meaning, methodologies, and geographical foci are continuously inscribed without entirely erasing earlier theoretical foundations. Through bibliometric analysis, we have charted its transition from a normative European spatial planning concept into a globally applied analytical framework. This trajectory is marked by prolific growth post-2010, a significant shift in epistemic gravity towards the East—notably China—and a profound methodological maturation, evidenced by the divergence between foundational, highly-cited works and pioneering, densely networked research with high PageRank.

However, this dynamic evolution is juxtaposed with persistent structural challenges that threaten to stifle innovation. Firstly, a discursive monopoly and geographical bias are evident, as knowledge production remains concentrated within a few academic hubs in China and Europe. This hegemony risks cementing a dominant discourse and facilitating the uncritical transfer of context-specific theories to diverse urban realities, potentially constraining innovative research to a narrow set of well-studied regions. Secondly, network analyses reveal a strongly clustered, 'siloes' intellectual structure. While this clustering enables analytical depth, it has also fostered disconnects between sub-fields—such as physical versus social approaches, or organic European versus engineered Chinese models—thereby impeding the interdisciplinary dialogue necessary for genuine paradigm shifts. Thirdly, a critical marginalisation of social dimensions persists; core issues like spatial justice, social cohesion, and community resilience remain peripheral, addressed in less than 15% of the literature, despite their centrality to the concept's early normative promises.

To address these challenges, we conclude by outlining a clear agenda for future research that builds directly upon the gaps identified in our analysis. This agenda prioritises three strategic axes. The first is a shift from static analysis to socio-spatial dynamics, leveraging big data and machine learning to dynamically model how polycentric structures affect social equity, access to services, and community resilience over time. The second involves developing contextualizing frameworks via global collaboration. To dismantle the existing discursive monopoly, it is essential to create flexible, context-sensitive theoretical and measurement frameworks in

partnership with scholars from the Global South, fostering a deeper understanding of polycentricity in under-studied regions of Africa, Latin America, and South Asia. The third axis focuses on bridging theory and governance practice, with a critical priority being the comparative analysis of multi-level governance models and policy mechanisms—both financial and institutional—for managing competition and fostering cooperation among urban centres.

Ultimately, achieving a more integrated and robust paradigm for 21st-century urban analysis necessitates a conscious effort to foster critical dialogue between schools of thought, promote inclusive international collaborations, and accord simultaneous attention to the economic, environmental, and—crucially—the social dimensions of polycentricity. This roadmap charts a course toward a more scientifically rigorous, equitable, and policy-relevant next generation of research.

Study Limitations

This study's reliance on the Scopus database may overlook significant non-English literature and policy documents, potentially excluding critical perspectives from non-Anglophone contexts. Furthermore, the focus on journal articles excludes book-based publications, possibly marginalising key contributions from fields like economic geography and institutional urban economics. While systematic searches were employed, the use of “polycentricity” as an umbrella term may slightly reduce analytical precision, and some relevant studies not using the term in titles/keywords may have been omitted. Finally, while normative policy agendas (e.g., EU policy) influence research, they were excluded from this analysis as they fall outside its scope.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this research, the writing of this manuscript, or its publication.

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